

Guidelines

for service managers

summary

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visual summary

CREATE AN ACCOUNT

GO TO YOUR DASHBOARD

FILL OUT THE PERSONAL PROFILE

**CREATE A SERVICE:
ORGANIZATION - TOOL -
METHOD - SERVICE**

MANAGE THE ACCESS

The new E-RIHS Catalogue of Services (CoS) features an advanced dashboard system designed to streamline and manage access activities. This system includes four distinct dashboards, each tailored to support the four different actors involved – User (U), User Helpdesk (UH), Service Manager (SM), and Reviewer (R) – facilitating the organization and management of access to ensure optimal performance for research and its results.

Each Dashboard offers different levels of access to the information and data it contains:

- **User (U)** – This is the basic access level. The Dashboard provides a standard set of features, allowing Users to update their profiles and manage their proposals.
- **User Helpdesk (UH)** – The UH moderates and oversees the entire process, assigning different roles through its dashboard. The UH can communicate and share information with Users, Reviewers, and Service Managers.
- **Reviewer (R)** – The Reviewer evaluates proposals that have passed the feasibility check and provides comments on the evaluation.
- **Service Manager (SM)** – The Service Manager is the main contact person responsible for managing access at a facility (previously known as a provider). Their primary tasks include assessing the feasibility of proposals and organizing and facilitating access through a co-creation process with the User.

This handbook specifically provides guidelines for:

Service Manager

You can browse the Catalogue of Services from the E-RIHS website or directly at the link: catalogue.e-rihs.eu

Catalogue of services

Search

Find the services you need quickly and easily

Filters

Reset filters

Platforms

- Archlab 3
- Digilab 3
- Fixlab 1
- Molab 3

Organizations

Select an option

Countries

Select an option

Techniques

Select an option

Materials

Select an option

Fields of application

Select an option

10 results

Lux Allowance Online Calculator [↗](#)

This Lux allowance calculator is used to check the calculated light exposure (in lux hours) for an object or group of objects for a selected period of display. This is based on three parameters:

- **Platforms:** Digilab
- **Tools:** Lux-Allowance-Calculator
- **Techniques:** Data processing

Organization

The National Gallery | Uk

Add to Proposal

Save for later

Microprofilometric Data analysis [↗](#)

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing Lorem Ipsum passages, and more recently with desktop publishing software like Aldus PageMaker including versions of Lorem Ipsum.

- **Platforms:** Digilab
- **Tools:** Cono22
- **Techniques:** 3d laser scanning

Organization

National Institute of Optics | Italy

Add to Proposal

Save for later

Data analysis [↗](#)

In our increasingly data-driven world, it's more important than ever to have accessible ways to view and understand data. After all, the demand for data skills in employees is steadily increasing each year. Employees and business owners at every level need to have an understanding of data and of its impact. That's where data visualization comes in handy. With the goal of making data more accessible and understandable, data visualization in the form of dashboards is the go-to tool for many businesses to analyze and share information.

- **Platforms:** Digilab
- **Tools:** Data enhancer PRO

Add to Proposal

Save for later

Go to the link: catalogue.e-rihs.eu and click “Sign in” (on the top right).

You can log in with your **ORCID account**, this is the **recommended method**. If you don't have one, we suggest you to create one at: <https://orcid.org/>

You may also create an E-RIHS account using your email address by clicking “Register.”

 You will receive a **verification link** to activate your account. **Once done, please contact the E-RIHS User Helpdesk to request assignment of the "Service Manager" role.**

 mail to: helpdesk@e-rihs.eu

Forgot your password?

No worries! Resetting your password is a breeze. Just enter the email you registered with in E-RIHS

We have emailed your password reset link.

Email *

Send a link to reset

Remembered your password? [Try again](#)

The term '**Service Manager**' (or '**Contact Person of the Facility**') refers to the individual responsible for managing a service at an E-RIHS facility. The Service Manager is in charge of:

- creating, describing and updating the service/s details in the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services,
- evaluating the feasibility of a proposal and
- coordinating the access visit with the User Group Leader who submitted the proposal.

Service Managers can also function as Users, enabling them to submit proposals to institutions **outside their own organization**.

Once logged in, you will access your **Dashboard**: this is the place where you can act as a Service Manager and as a User. A general view of the dashboard is shown below.

From “**List of applications**”, you can evaluate the feasibility of each proposal you are involved as a Service Manager. You can also take actions for proposals in which you are the User.

From here, you can edit your **Profile** and insert your **Organization**, you can also browse the CoS or write a proposal.

From “**Proposals**”, you can read the complete list of the proposals, included those you are not involved.

In “**Post access Reports**”, you can read the Post Access Reports, once submitted by the User.

In “**Settings**”, you can create or modify a service you manage, filling out the different components. More precise you are, more your service/s can be discoverable in the catalogue!!

The **Settings** section of the dashboard will become visible **once you contact the User Helpdesk and are assigned the Service Manager role**.

You are requested to complete your Profile with **detailed information** about your professional background and your Organization.

The screenshot shows the E-RIHS Profile page with the following sections:

- My details:**
 - Personal title: Mrs
 - Name: Irene
 - Surname: Dei Gratta
 - Email: irene.deigratta5@gmail.com
 - City: FIRENZE
 - Country: FI
 - Nationality: Italy
 - Birth year: 1972
 - Gender: Female
- Institutional information:**
 - Home institution (HI): Istituto Nazionale di Ottica
 - HI Legal Status Code: Public Research Organization
 - HI Country Code: Italy
 - Institution address: Largo E. Fermi, 6
 - Institution city: Florence
 - Function / Job / Title: Technologist
 - Position: Post-Doc Researcher
 - Phone (Office):
 - Academic Background: humanist
- Background:**
 - Short Curriculum Vitae: Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was

Buttons: Cancel, Save changes

When logging in with an **ORCID account**, please **review** all imported information, especially your **name and email address**. Make sure to update any details as needed to ensure accuracy.

EG. If your ORCID account is not public or enriched, it is probable that the system will fill the email item with a “strange” email:

Email*

0009-0001-1012-9786@orcid

After completing your personal profile, click on the E-RIHS logo to return to the dashboard, then go to “Settings” and fill in the “Organization” field.

The “Organization Details” tab in your **Profile** will remain empty until you create an Organization or are added as a Service Manager to an Organization created by someone else.

The "Organization Details" tab shows all organizations associated with your profile. From this list, you can select the Organization for which you are serving as the Service Manager.

In the "List of Applications," you'll find the list of proposals that involve you as a **Service Manager** or as a **User**.

If you click on the "Manage" button, a submenu with four different options will open: "General Information", "Application History", "Check Feasibility" and "Update Files".

click on **Manage!**

In the "List of Applications," you, as the Service Manager, can review proposals that require a feasibility assessment by selecting "Waiting Feasibility" in the top menu. Additionally, you can check the "In/Under Review" status of proposals where you are assigned as the User Group Leader or User.

When you act as a **User**, you will find:

- **General information** - you can download the proposal as a PDF (using the “Download PDF” button in the top right corner)
- **Application history** - you’ll find all the steps and status associated with that proposal
- **Update files** - you can update or upload the files related to the ownership or drone flights permissions.

The screenshot displays the user interface for managing applications. The top navigation bar includes a search icon and the text 'Sec'. The main content area is divided into two sections: 'General information' and 'Proposal files'.

General information section:

- Navigation: My Applications > Analisi sul Bacco di Michelangelo > General information
- Buttons: General information, Application history, Update files
- Section: **Analisi sul Bacco di Michelangelo**
- Fields: ID proposal (8), Submission date (21/10/2024, 15:13:13), User group leader (Irene Del Gratta, irenedelgratta5@gmail.com)
- Section: **Partners**
- Section: **Services**
- Text: Scanning VIS-NIR multispectral reflectography
- Table:

Feasibility	Feasible
Comment	Molto benissimo
Contact persons	Diego Quintero, diegoivan.quinterobalbaso, Diego Quintero, diegoivan.quinterobalbaso
- Button: **Download PDF** (highlighted with a red circle and arrow)

Proposal files section:

- Navigation: My Applications > Analisi sul Bacco di Michelangelo > Proposal files
- Section: **Proposal files**
- Section: **Molab**
- Text: Add a description for each object. Click the button and complete the form based on the number of objects.
- Form: Object description, Ownership (Museo del Bargello, Firenze), Molab object ownership consent (Requested, Received, Other), Molab object ownership consent file (010A2177CAC8RZAVCONFPSSDNPS.pdf), Authorization request for drone flights (if applicable) (Requested, Received, Other, Non Applicable), Outline specific logistic preparations (scaffolding etc.), risks and safety hazards (as applicable) (not applicable), Should MOLAB X-ray based instrumentations be requested, have any national radiation protection measures (licenses/accreditations) and the duration for their request been pre-determined? (Yes, No)
- Text: Fully describe any logistic preparations necessary for access as well as any risk or hazards during the access. Note that the costs incurred are at the expense of the user. Specific security issues should be mentioned. Please write "Not applicable" if needed.
- Button: **Save**

Application history section:

- Navigation: My Applications > Analisi sul Bacco di Michelangelo > Application history
- Buttons: General information, Application history, Update files
- Section: **Application history**
- Table:

2024-10-21 15:13:13	The application has been created
2024-10-21 15:13:13	The application has been updated as Submitted
2024-10-25 08:47:56	The application has been updated as Feasible

When you act as a **Service Manager**, you will find:

- **General information** - you can download the proposal as a PDF (using the "Download PDF" button in the top right corner)
- **Application history** - you'll find all the steps and status associated with that proposal
- **Check feasibility** - this item appears ONLY when you have to evaluate the feasibility of a specific proposal. To perform the feasibility check, mark the proposal as feasible or not feasible. A pop-up will appear, allowing you to add comments that will be readable only to the User Helpdesk and Reviewers.

In “List of applications”, you can search or filter the list of applications on:

- Name
- Acronym

The screenshot displays the 'My Applications' page. At the top, there is a breadcrumb 'My Applications > List' and a title 'My Applications'. Below the title are filter tabs: 'All 1', 'In Review 0', and 'Waiting Feasibility 1'. A search bar is located on the right. A 'Sort by' dropdown menu is open, showing options for 'Name' and 'Acronym'. The main content area shows a single application entry: '12 - Title Proposal ABC', with details 'Acronym: TPABC', 'Type: NEW', and 'Status: Submitted'. A 'Manage' button is visible below the entry. At the bottom, it indicates 'Showing 1 result' and a 'Per page 10' dropdown.

This section offers essential guidelines for creating a New Service on the E-RIHS CoS platform. Please review these guidelines carefully before submitting your Service, as the information you provide will help populate the service catalog search engine and assist potential users in finding the most suitable service for their research needs. To complete a service listing, please fill out the **four forms** available in the **Settings** menu of your Dashboard in the order they are presented:

1. Organizations
2. Tools
3. Methods
4. Services

 Before proceeding with creating a new **Service**, we recommend taking advantage of your experience with users and their research needs to thoughtfully structure it – considering the number of Tools and Methods you include. This approach will help you create a comprehensive catalogue that aligns closely with their requirements.

**YOUR
ORGANIZATION**

TOOL:

CONFOCAL RAMAN MICROSCOPE

METHOD 1:

**PROCEDURE YOU USE
FOR THE ANALYSIS**

**SERVICE 1:
SPOT ANALYSIS FOR
CHEMICAL
CHARACTERIZATION**

METHOD 2:

**PROCEDURE YOU USE
FOR THE ANALYSIS**

**SERVICE 2:
MICRO-CHEMICAL
MAPPING**

METHOD 3:

**PROCEDURE YOU USE
FOR THE ANALYSIS**

**SERVICE 3:
CONFOCAL ANALYSIS OF
TRANSPARENT AND
SEMITRANSPARENT LAYERS**

In the **Organizations** section, you can create a New Organization or manage your organizations' profile.

Create a **New Organization**

Organizations > List

Organizations

New organization

Search

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Acronym	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Institute of Optics	INO	Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	Opificio delle Pietre Dure	OPD	Edit

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 results

Per page 10

Manage an Organization

When creating a New Organization, please provide the following information. Fields marked with a red asterisk (*) are required. For more details on a specific field, click the question mark icon (?) for additional guidance.

Organizations > Create

Create Organization

Name*

Acronym*

Email of the organization*

Phone

Logo URL ?

Based in

Organization type*

Joined the field date ?

Research Disciplines*

Service managers

Organizations > Create

Create Organization

Name*	Acronym*
<input type="text" value="Select an option"/>	<input type="text"/>
Email of the organization*	Phone
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Logo URL <input type="text" value="URL to an image representing the organization"/>	Based in <input type="text" value="Start typing to select an item"/>
Organization type* <input type="text" value="New tag"/>	Joined the field date <input type="text" value="gg/mm/aaaa"/>
Research Disciplines* <input type="text" value="Start typing to select an item"/>	Service managers <input type="text" value="Your email"/>

When creating a New Organization, your email will automatically be added, and your profile will be linked to it by default. You can add additional Service Managers by selecting their emails in the “Service Managers” field. Please note that **only the emails of individuals who are already registered will appear in the list**. Ensure you include only those who are actively working as Service Managers within your Organization.

If multiple Service Managers are associated to a single Organization, we recommend contacting your colleagues before creating an Organization to avoid duplicates and to ensure that all required profiles can be linked to a single Organization.

The Name and Acronym fields are linked to the Research Organization Registry (ROR). As you start typing, a drop-down menu with matching options will appear. The name of your Organization will be displayed in the language in which it was registered in ROR.

If your Organization is not listed, you can add it by clicking the plus icon (+).

To add an organization not listed in ROR

Email of the organization (**optional**) - here you can include an alternative email from your research group or institution that can be used to manage the access to the Service.

The date on which your Organization started working in Heritage Science.

Logo URL (**optional**) - A link to the logo that represents your Organization.

You can scroll the full list following this link:
<https://research.ng-london.org.uk/ecls/?group=g10>

Here your email will appear automatically if you are the creator of the item. If you need it, you can add the email of other Service Managers **already registered in the CoS system** belonging to your Organizations.

In the Citation section (**optional**), you may provide a URL linking to supplementary materials about your Organization, such as references, user testimonials, or usage guides. To add additional items not listed, click the plus icon (+).

The screenshot shows the 'Citation' section of the settings interface. It includes a 'Citation' text input field, a 'URL' text input field, and a 'Reference type' dropdown menu. The dropdown menu is currently set to 'Select an option' and has a plus icon (+) next to it, which is circled in red.

You may provide one or more links to an external repository or archive associated with your institution, such as [arXiv](#), [ORCID](#), [DOI](#), or others not listed in the options. To add these, click the plus icon (+).

The screenshot shows the 'External pid' section of the settings interface. It includes a 'Pid type' dropdown menu and a 'PID' text input field. The dropdown menu is currently set to 'Select an option' and has a plus icon (+) next to it, which is circled in red. A red arrow points to the plus icon with the text 'PID means Persistent Identifier'. Another red arrow points to the 'Add external PID' button with the text 'Click here to add another PID'.

Lastly, you may include one or more links to your institution's website. This link will be displayed in the Catalogue.

The screenshot shows the 'Webpages' section of the settings interface. It includes a 'URL' text input field and an 'Add webpage' button. The button is circled in red, and a red arrow points to it with the text 'Click here to add another Website'.

Once all the fields are completed, you can click on “Create” button at the bottom of the form. A pop-up notification will appear in the bottom right corner of your screen to confirm that your Organization has been successfully created.

If you are editing an existing Organization, save your changes by clicking the “**Save changes**” button. A pop-up notification will appear in the bottom right corner of your screen to confirm that your Organization has been successfully saved.

 THIS SECTION IS NOT FOR ARCHLAB!

The **Tools** section functions similarly to the Organizations section. In the general tool list, you can create new Tools or manage those you have already saved. Use the filter in the upper right corner of the list to select Tools based on their associated Organization.

Create a new Tool

Tools > List

Tools

[New tool](#)

Q Search

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Description	Organization	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Multispectral scanner	The multispectral scanner developed at CNR-INO is...	National Institute of Optics	<input type="checkbox"/> Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	Portable Raman Spectroscopy	The Bravo spectrometer uses a patented technology...	National Institute of Optics	<input type="checkbox"/> Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cono22	Software for processing laser microprofilometric d...	National Institute of Optics	<input type="checkbox"/> Edit

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 results

Per page 10

Edit a Tool

There are two types of **Tools**: Equipment and Software. To begin, select the appropriate type of Tool you wish to create; the form will then display the relevant fields for each type.

Provide a name for your Tool and select your Organization from the drop-down menu. **Please note that only the Organizations you have created will appear in this list.**

In the designated field, describe the Tool clearly and concisely to help potential Users make an informed selection. For more details on a specific field, click the question mark icon (?) for additional guidance. Fields marked with a red asterisk (*) are required.

The screenshot shows the 'Create Tool' form with the following fields and annotations:

- Tools > Create** (breadcrumb)
- Create Tool** (title)
- Tool type**: Radio buttons for **Equipment** (selected) and **Software**.
- Name***: Text input field.
- Organization***: Dropdown menu with 'Select an option'.
- Description***: Text area with annotation: "The information you provide will assist the Users in selecting the most suitable Service for their Research Needs."
- Output data types***: Text input field with 'New tag' and annotation: "This field will display a list of possible data types, select the most adequate to describe the type of Outputs of your Tool. You can select more than one."
- Acquisition Areas**: Text input field with 'New tag' and annotation: "Select the best option to describe the area your Tool is capable to investigate. From a small spot to a large area."
- Last checked date***: Date picker with 'gg/mm/aaaa' and calendar icon.
- Last calibration date**: Date picker with 'gg/mm/aaaa', calendar icon, and tooltip: "Date when the equipment was last calibrated. ?"
- Manufacturer**: Text input field.
- Model**: Text input field.
- Serial number**: Text input field.
- Impact on object or sample**: Text input field with 'Start typing to select an item' and annotation: "Select the best option from the list that describes the Impact of the equipment on the object, for example, 'non-invasive', 'destructive', etc."

You can include additional details about your Tool, such as the “Working distance” and “Links” to supplementary information, like a manufacturer brochure or a publication describing a prototype. If the type of link you need is not available in the list, you can always add a new one by clicking the plus icon (+).

Working distance

Start typing to select an item

Link

Type

Select an option

Link

Add Link

Create Create & create another Cancel

Once all fields are completed, you can create the new Tool by clicking the **Create** button at the bottom of the form. A pop-up will confirm that you have successfully created a Tool.

When creating a **Software Tool**, you will be asked to provide additional fields, including the “License type”, “Developer name”, and “Version”.

Output data types

New tag

License Type

Start typing to select an item

Acquisition Areas

New tag

Input Data types

Start typing to select an item

Last checked date

gg/mm/aaaa

Release date

gg/mm/aaaa

Developer

Software version

You can edit your **Tools** at any time. Please keep the information up to date to ensure Users have access to the latest version of your Tool. After making your desired changes, save the Tool by clicking the **Save Changes** button at the bottom of the form.

If you wish to remove a Tool that is no longer available, click on the **Delete** button in the upper right corner of the Tool form. A pop-up will appear asking you to confirm the deletion. Once confirmed, you will receive a notification that the Tool has been successfully deleted.

This is the final view of your **Tool** in the E-RIHS CoS. Here, you can see how the information you've provided is displayed.

The screenshot shows the final view of a tool in the E-RIHS CoS. The page is titled "Tool: Portable IR spectrometer" and includes several sections with red arrows pointing to specific information:

- Name:** Points to the tool title "Tool: Portable IR spectrometer".
- Organization:** Points to the organization name "Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche 'Giulio Natta'" in the organization box.
- Last check date:** Points to the date "04-11-2024" in the last checked date box.
- Description:** Points to the detailed text describing the Bruker Optics ALPHA-R spectrometer.
- Output types:** Points to the "Dataset/Data package (images, spectra, other)" option.
- Impact on object:** Points to the "Noninvasive (no physical alteration)" option.
- Manufacturer & Model:** Points to the "Buker Optics" manufacturer and "Alpha II" model.
- Acquisition area:** Points to the "small spot 27mm2" option.
- Working distances:** Points to the "Near-contact (< 0.01 m)" option.

The **Methods** section enables Service Managers to outline how each **Tool** is utilized within a specific **Service**. This setup allows for flexibility, as a Tool can be applied across multiple Methods, and a single Method may incorporate various Tools.

In the general Methods list, you can create new Methods or manage existing ones that you (or a Service Manager of your Organization) have already created. Use the filter in the upper-right corner to view Tools by your affiliated Organization.

Here you can create a **New Method**

A screenshot of the "Methods" list page. The page title is "Methods > List" and "Methods". There is a "New method" button in the top right corner. Below it is a search bar and a filter icon. The main content is a table with three columns: "Name", "Organization", and "Edit". The table contains three rows of data. At the bottom, there is a pagination control showing "Showing 1 to 3 of 3 results" and "Per page 10". Red arrows point from the text "Here you can create a New Method" to the "New method" button and from "To Edit a Method click here" to the "Edit" links in the table.

To **Edit** a Method click here

Provide a name for your **Method**, for example: “Microchemical mapping” or “Thickness measurement”, and select your Organization from the drop-down menu. Please note that only the Methods you have created will appear in this list.

In the field “Description”, describe the Method procedure clearly and concisely to help potential Users make an informed selection. For more details on a specific field, click the question mark icon (?) for additional guidance. Fields marked with a red asterisk (*) are required.

The screenshot shows the 'Create Method' form with the following fields and their associated help text:

- Title***: A text input field.
- Organization***: A dropdown menu with the text 'Select an option'.
- Description**: A text area with a help tooltip: 'The general technique that this Method is an application of. If none is applicable, choose 'other' and specify the technique in 'Technique (other)' field.'
- Relevant Technique***: A dropdown menu with a help tooltip: 'The type of method this represents. Examples are 'Analysis Method', 'Research support', 'Workflow'.'
- Method type**: A text input field.
- Method version***: A text input field with a help tooltip: 'e.g: 1.0.4, 2-alpha-324'.
- Other Techniques (if necessary)**: A text input field with a help icon.
- Alternative labels**: A section with a text input field and a trash icon.
- Alternative codes, labels or names**: A text input field.

Red arrows point from the help text boxes to the corresponding fields in the form. A larger red arrow points from the 'Alternative labels' section towards the bottom left of the page.

For **ARCHLAB** managers, please insert “Archlab access service” here and if you want include other techniques, put them in “Other techniques”

You can add alternative labels to your Method that can help the Users to discover your Service for example acronyms or synonyms commonly used in the field.

Alternative labels

Alternative codes, labels or names

Add to alternative labels

To add an alternative label click here

Method parameter

Parameter type*

Select an option

Value unit*

Select an option

Value*

Core method Value

Parameter Unit*

Select an option

Parameter Specific Related Tool

Add to method parameter

Create Cancel

To add a parameter click here

Specify the tool associated with this parameter here.

THIS SECTION IS NOT FOR
ARCHLAB!
please delete the block

Select the type and unit for each parameter used in the Method, specifying details like “wavelength” or “pressure”. If a required parameter is not available in the list, add it by clicking the plus icon (+).

The **Value unit** list includes three types of data:

- **Number:** A data type for numeric values, including integers and decimals.
- **String:** A sequence of characters, typically used for text.
- **Boolean:** A data type with two possible values - true or false.

Alternative labels

Alternative codes, labels or names

Add to alternative labels

Any alternative codes, label or names for the method (Not for the technique or tools). This could be an acronym or a full text name. If an acronym, it is used as the preferred label. This is used for search and discovery purposes.

Method parameter

Value unit* ! THIS SECTION IS NOT FOR ARCHLAB! Value* Core method Value

Parameter Unit* Parameter type*

Parameter Specific Related Tool

Add to method parameter

Create Create & create another Cancel

Created

Once all fields are completed, you can create the new **Method** by clicking the **Create** button at the bottom of the form. A pop-up will confirm that you have successfully created a Method.

Save changes Cancel

Saved

To save changes when editing a Method, click on the button at the bottom of the form. A confirmation pop-up will appear once the Method is successfully created. To delete a Method, click the Delete button in the upper-right corner and confirm in the pop-up.

Methods > Edit

Edit Method

Title*

Test1

Delete Method

Are you sure you would like to do this?

Cancel Confirm

Delete

This is the final view of your **Method** in the E-RIHS CoS. Here, you can see how the information you've provided is displayed.

Title

Organization

Alternative labels

Description

Techniques

Other techniques

Method Type

Version

Parameters

The screenshot shows the final view of a method in the E-RIHS CoS. The page is titled 'Method: External reflection IR spectroscopy' and is associated with the organization 'Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche "Giulio Natta"'. The page includes sections for Alternative labels, Description, Techniques, Other techniques, Method Type, Version, and Parameters. Red arrows point to the Title, Organization, Alternative labels, Description, Techniques, and Version sections.

Alternative labels
External reflection IR spectroscopy ERIRS

Description
The relevance of external reflection IR spectroscopy in heritage science has experienced a constant grow in the last two decades owing to analytical peculiarities that make it an extremely useful tool to answer the questions posed by the study and conservation of art-historical and archaeological materials. High versatility, sensitivity, molecular specificity, noninvasiveness and contactless are all crucial requirements that IR spectroscopy fulfils allowing for comprehensive compositional studies of artworks and cultural heritage materials (inorganic and organic materials). External reflection is a non-contact acquisition mode in which light propagates from a medium (i.e. air with $n = 1$) toward a sample (with $n > 1$). In these conditions two types of reflection take place: surface reflection and volume reflection. Surface reflection also called front-surface reflection since it corresponds to light which is not (or slightly) penetrating the analysed surface. It is ruled by the Fresnel's law at a normal incidence depends on the real part (n , representing the light dispersion) and the imaginary part (ik , with k representing the absorption index) of the complex refractive index \tilde{n} ($\tilde{n} = n + ik$) as it follows: $R = \frac{[n - 1]^2 + k^2}{[n + 1]^2 + k^2}$ Where n has a typical dispersion with the wavenumbers and assumes a derivative-like profile in correspondence of the absorption bands; k is proportional to the absorption coefficient of the Lambert Beers law thus it changes along the wavenumber axis similarly to an IR absorption profile. When $k \ll 1$ (most of the organic compounds, including polymeric systems) R follows mainly the behaviour of n , namely inflection points replace the IR absorption bands. When $k \gg 1$ (inorganic compounds containing oxyanions, i.e. carbonates, sulphates, phosphates), R tends to unity. The strong absorption hampers radiation to penetrate the sample in that energy range due to the strong change of n ; as a result, light is mainly reflected (at these wavenumbers the sample behaves as a metallic surface) giving rise to a maximum of reflection at the maximum absorption (inverted band); this phenomenon is better known as reststrahlen effect. In volume reflection, IR penetrates the sample undergoing refraction, reflection, and scattering prior to be reflected out from the surface in all the directions (in fact it is also called diffuse reflection). Volume reflection gives rise to spectra like those recorded in transmission mode, but with variation in the band relative intensities and with band broadening mainly linked to the degree of light penetration. In external reflection mode, generally, cultural heritage materials show spectral distortions arising from the variable contributions of both volume and surface reflection, depending from the roughness and absorption properties of the sample surface which vary along the IR spectral range (generally including both the mid and near IR ranges 10000-350 cm^{-1}).

Techniques
Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

Other techniques
infrared spectroscopy

Method Type
Analysis Method

Version
1.0

Parameters

Type: minimum wavenumber Unit: cm^{-1} Value: 350	Type: maximum wavenumber Unit: cm^{-1} Value: 8000	Type: spectral resolution Unit: cm^{-1} Value: 4	Type: spectral representation Unit: none Value: pseudo-absorbance	Type: spectral representation Unit: none Value: reflectance
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This is the final step in creating a new **Service**. In this section, you'll connect all previously created entities – Organizations, Tools, and Methods. The form follows a similar format to previous ones: required fields are marked with a red asterisk (*), and you can click on the question mark icon (?) for additional information on any specific field.

Here you can create a New Service

A screenshot of the "Services" list page. At the top left, it says "Services > List" and "Services" in bold. On the top right, there is a "New service" button. Below this is a search bar with a magnifying glass icon and the word "Search". A red circle highlights a filter icon (a funnel) next to the search bar. Below the search bar is a table with columns for "Title" and "Organization". The table contains six rows of service entries, each with a checkbox on the left and an "Edit" button on the right. At the bottom of the table, it says "Showing 1 to 6 of 6 results" and "Per page 10" with a dropdown arrow.

To Edit a Service click here

Here, you will link your **Service** to an **Organization**. Select the relevant **Organization** from your list.

Select the role(s) of your **Organization**, such as data acquisition, data interpretation, and others.

The screenshot shows the 'Create Service' form with the following fields and annotations:

- Organization**: A dropdown menu with the placeholder text 'Select an option'. A red arrow points to this field.
- Organization role**: A dropdown menu with the placeholder text 'Start typing to select an item'. A red arrow points to this field.
- Title**: A text input field with a tooltip that reads: 'Service title. For an ARCHLAB service, this could be e.g. 'Access to KIK-IRPA Archives'; for the other platforms, this could be the name of the technique.'
- Readiness level**: A dropdown menu with the placeholder text 'Start typing to select an item' and a tooltip that reads: 'A brief description of a specific technical or access service offered, such as the use of X to investigate Y'.
- Summary**: A text input field with a tooltip that reads: 'A brief description of a specific technical or access service offered, such as the use of X to investigate Y'.
- Operating language**: A dropdown menu with the placeholder text 'Start typing to select an item' and a tooltip that reads: 'What languages can the team operate in or what language is a tool presented in'.
- Version**: A text input field with the example text 'e.g: 1.0.4, 2-alpha-324'.
- Version date**: A text input field with the placeholder 'gg/mm/aaaa'.
- Service access period unit**: A dropdown menu with the placeholder text 'Start typing to select an item'.
- Service Access Hours per Unit**: A text input field.
- Service Access Unit Cost**: A text input field.

The readiness level list is based on **Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)**, a framework established by the European Union to estimate technology maturity. TRLs are divided into nine levels:

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1. Basic principles observed
 2. Concept formulated
 3. Experimental proof of concept
 4. Technology validated in a lab setting
 5. Concept validated in a Heritage Science environment
 6. Service demonstrated in a Heritage Science environment
 7. Operational system prototype demonstrated
 8. Service complete and qualified
 9. Service proven in an operational environment

For **Archlab**, we recommend selecting level 9.

In the form, you can provide all relevant information regarding access to your Service, including the Access Unit (e.g., Week, Days, Hours), the Hours per Unit, and the Platform Type (Archlab, Fixlab, Molab, or Digilab).

The screenshot shows the 'Create Service' form with the following fields and their current states:

- Organization***: Select an option (dropdown)
- Organization role***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown)
- Title***: (empty text field)
- Readiness level***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown)
- Summary***: (empty text area)
- Operating language***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown)
- Version**: (empty text field)
- Version date**: gg/mm/yyyy (calendar icon)
- Service access period unit***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown). A tooltip explains: "Insert here the unit used for the service expressed in days, hours, etc. The Service Access Period Unit is a measure specifying the access offered to the users, which may vary; e.g. precise values like hours or sessions of beam time processing time".
- Service Access Hours per Unit**: (empty text field)
- Service Access Unit Cost**: (empty text field)
- Technique**: Start typing to select an item (dropdown). A tooltip explains: "A list of the individual relevant heritage science examination and analytical techniques carried out within this Service. If none of the techniques is applicable, use the 'Other service techniques' field.".
- E-RIHS Platform***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown)
- Research disciplines***: Start typing to select an item (dropdown)
- Service managers***: A red callout box with the text "Your email" and a red arrow points to this dropdown menu.
- Limitations**: (empty text field)
- Description***: (empty text area). A tooltip explains: "A longer description/documentation of a specific technical or access service offered under E-RIHS. This description will be shown in the catalogue. Please be accurate and clear".

You may also add more than one Service Manager – someone who can help you manage access to your Services. **To do so, ensure that the SM is registered in the CoS system**; their name will then be available for selection from the drop-down menu.

Please upload a relevant image to represent your Service, as visuals help attract potential users. Simply drag and drop the file into the field, or browse your computer to select it.

The screenshot shows a form for creating a service. The 'Picture' field is highlighted with a red arrow pointing to the 'Drag & Drop your files or Browse' text. The 'Research Questions' section has a red arrow pointing to the 'Research question' input field. A tooltip for the 'Picture' field reads: 'Please upload a 440x286 pixels jpeg image'. A tooltip for the 'Output description' field reads: 'A description of all the raw and processed outputs created by the service including details of how they relate to or rely on each other.' A tooltip for the 'Input description' field reads: 'A description of the required formats or files required by the service'. A tooltip for the 'Research Questions' field reads: 'Add here the research questions that the service addresses. Example: Can we consult microscope images and analytical results on paint cross sections? How can I observe underdrawings? How can I identify the pigments in a painting?'.

 Research Questions help align Services with users' specific research needs. Write one or more questions that your Service can help answer, ensuring that the same keywords appear in both the Research Questions and the fields used to describe the Service.

For instance, if your question is: "How can I identify inorganic pigments?", it's beneficial to include keywords like "pigments," "identify," or "inorganic" in the description or other relevant fields.

Also **Functions** provide a brief, practical description for the User, such as "Material Analysis."

You can add multiple Research Questions/Functions by clicking on the Add Function/Research Questions button.

The screenshot shows the 'Functions' section of the service settings form. A red circle highlights the 'Add function' button at the bottom. A tooltip for the 'Function' field reads: 'Short and descriptive service practical level activities, what has a service been used for, what is it intended for. E.g. 'Materials Analysis', 'Dye Analysis', 'De-convolution XRF Spectra', 'Calculating Light Exposure Allowance'.'

The final section of the Service form is dedicated to Service contacts (if different from your email as Service Manager), a detailed description of measurable properties, and additional relevant links.

In the **Measurable Property** field, a list of properties will appear. If the property you need isn't listed, you can add it by clicking on the plus icon (+). The same functionality applies to the **Materials** list; note that this list will also appear in the CoS and be linked to filters, enabling users to search for and select services more broadly.

The screenshot displays the 'Service contacts' section of a form. It includes an 'Add contact' button and a tooltip that reads 'Measurable properties and materials that can be studied by this service'. Below this is the 'Measurable properties' section, which features a dropdown menu with a plus icon (+) circled in red. The dropdown is divided into three columns: 'Measurable property', 'Materials', and 'Other materials'. Each column has a 'Select an option' dropdown with a plus icon (+) circled in red. An 'Add measurable property' button is located below the dropdowns. At the bottom of the form is the 'Links' section with an 'Add link' button.

Service active Can be added to a proposal

You will be able to insert Methods and Tools after you have created the service.

Create

Create & create another

Cancel

Two important options are available at the bottom of the form: Make “Service Active” and Allow Your Service to “Be Added to a Proposal”.

Service active

When your Service is marked as active, it will be visible in the E-RIHS CoS.

Can be added to a proposal

By enabling the option to add your Service to a Proposal, Users can include it in their submissions.

You can disable this option if all available slots are filled, if there are instrumentation issues, or for any other reason requiring a temporary pause. In this case, if your Service remains active, it will still be visible in the CoS, and Users may be redirected to your Service’s website.

Service active Can be added to a proposal

Link to the service webpage*

?

make your service active & visible

Once created, associate your Service to Tools and Methods!!!

 After completing all fields, click the Create button to add the Service. Once the Service is created, you can link it to relevant Methods and Tool(s) previously set up. This information will then be visible in the CoS.

As with other forms, you can Edit or Delete your Services at any time. Keep your Service information up to date to ensure the latest version is always available in the E-RIHS CoS.

This is how your Service will appear in the E-RIHS CoS. By clicking on the arrow, you can open the Service page to view all the details you have entered.

Catalogue of services

Search

Find the services you need quickly and easily

Filters

Reset filters

Platforms

- Archlab 0
- Fixlab 1
- Molab 1

Organizations

Select an option

Countries

Select an option

Techniques

Select an option

Materials

Select an option

Fields of application

Select an option

2 results

External reflection IR spectroscopy [↗](#)

Add to Proposal

Save for later

External reflection IR spectroscopy is widely used in the field of heritage science for the characterization and identification of organic and inorganic materials.

Being a vibrational molecular spectroscopic technique, it provides information concerning the functional groups constituting the molecules ultimately aiding a molecular identification of unlimited materials under exam. The mid-FTIR range is particularly adapt for the recognition of inorganic materials (with some limitations from metal oxides) as well as synthetic and natural organic materials. This technique can provide information concerning any surface contaminations, alterations and products/processes of degrade. The NIR range, collected simultaneously, has also become an increasingly useful analytical tool by providing signals that are characteristic of infrared combination and overtone bands which have very low absorption coefficients. This region provides distinctive features regarding both the chemical composition of organic and inorganic compounds. As the NIR radiation is particularly penetrating, it can for example typically pass through paint layers and reach the ground layer of paintings providing information of pigments and binders alike.

Platforms: Molab

Tools: Portable IR spectrometer

Techniques: Data analysis, Data presentation, Data processing, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

External reflection IR spectroscopy [↗](#)

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Organization

Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche "Giulio Natta" | Italy

HUN-REN Institute for Nuclear Research | Hungary

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 results

Per page 10

This is the page of your Service in the E-RIHS CoS. Here, you can see how the information you've provided is displayed.

The screenshot shows a service page with the following sections and labels:

- Title:** Service: External reflection IR spectroscopy
- Summary:** External reflection IR spectroscopy is widely used in the field of heritage science for the characterization and identification of organic and inorganic materials.
- Description:** Being a vibrational molecular spectroscopic technique, it provides information concerning the functional groups constituting the molecules ultimately aiding a molecular identification of unlimited materials under exam.
- Limitations:** not suitable for artworks conserved in high humidity environment (>70RH%)
- Fields of application:** Chemistry, Heritage science (cultural heritage discipline), Materials science
- Materials:** Synthetic inorganic pigment, Inorganic materials, Synthetic resin, organic materials, Oil (organic material), Protein, Gum (material), Synthetic resin paint, Polymers, Inorganic pigment, Inorganic materials, organic materials, Salt (inorganic material), Soluble salt, Inorganic materials, organic materials
- Tools:** Portable IR spectrometer
- Methods:** External reflection IR spectroscopy
- Organization:** Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche "Giulio Natta", Italy
- Reference:** <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/psr-2018-0006/html>

Link to website or publications or datasets...

1 CALL OPENS

The User can browse the Catalogue and submit a proposal.

2 PROPOSAL SUBMISSION

Once the Proposal is submitted, the Service Manager immediately begins evaluating its feasibility (within 10 days).

3 PRE-FEASIBILITY

If the Proposal is not feasible or only partially feasible, the User has the opportunity to modify Services until the call deadline.
If the Proposal is feasible, it proceeds to the next steps.

4 CALL CLOSES

After the call closes, Proposals already marked as feasible retain that status.

The Service Manager must now evaluate the feasibility of Proposals that either didn't pass the first feasibility check or were newly submitted.

5 FEASIBILITY

Proposals marked as feasible after this second evaluation move on to the review process.

6 REVIEW PROCESS

The User Helpdesk ranks Proposals into three categories: Main list - Reserve list - Below threshold. The Service Manager receives an email informing them about the status of the Proposals they are involved in.

7 FORMULATING ACCESS OFFER

The User Helpdesk and the Service Manager collaborate to formulate the access offer.

The User must accept the access offer and upload any necessary permissions (e.g., ownership or drone flight permissions) before the access visit.

(continue to the next page)

8

ACCESS VISIT COORDINATION

Once the User accepts the access offer, an automatic email is sent to the Service Manager to coordinate and schedule the access visit. The Service Manager must click the "access scheduled" button on the Dashboard.

9

ACCESS CARRIED OUT

Once the access visit takes place, the Service Manager must click "Access Carried Out".

10

POST ACCESS REPORTS

For multi-service proposals, when all Service Managers confirm that access has been carried out, the system will prompt the User to submit the post-access duties within 2 months.

The system automatically sends a series of emails to the participants involved in the process. Specifically, during the registration, submission, evaluation, and post-access phases, the system automatically sends several emails to the Service Manager as reminders to perform certain actions or to inform them about the status of the Proposal. Below is an outline of the scheduled emails involving the Service Manager (SM), the User (U), the User Helpdesk (UH), and the Reviewer (R).

 helpdesk@e-rihs.eu

 www.e-rihs.eu

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